

PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM AND CONDITIONS OF DEVELOPING COMPETENCE IN USING MEDIA EDUCATIONAL TOOLS IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, media competence is considered in pedagogy in general as an integrative quality of a person, which is manifested in the selection, use, critical analysis, evaluation, creation, transmission and readiness to analyze the complex processes of media activity in society. given It was also mentioned about the development of the use of media education tools among teachers.

Introduction: In the period of transition to the information society, the non-traditional school model based on education requires the training of personnel based on the social order. With the sharp increase in the volume of all types of information in the information-educational environment, each new generation is faced with new conditions that require completely different knowledge. Therefore, a modern educational institution has the task of forming a positive-thinking, socially active person, developing the skills and competences of students to use the scope of information correctly, mastering innovative technologies, deepening and expanding knowledge, and learning independently. puts in front of z. Informatization of education sets new requirements for the quality of teachers' professional expertise and their level of training. In the context of improving education, the quality of future teacher training should be considered as a professional-specialist competence that characterizes the ability to use the acquired knowledge and experience in certain situations. The professional competence of teaching includes various structural, including media educational tools.

Among the main trends of world development, the transition to an information society is an important task, that is, the influence of media in all aspects of society is considered an urgent problem. According to the recommendation of the legislative meeting of the European Union Parliamentary Assembly, the production of software tools will stimulate the formation of media competence of young people and adults, and is also considered as an indispensable factor affecting the media culture of modern society. The components of the information society based on the environment of modern information and communication technologies are media, language and culture. It is the language and culture of the world we live in that is made up of human media competence. The importance of media competence in the world is emphasized in

the recommendations of various international organizations, including UNESCO, and the idea of developing the media competence of pedagogues is supported.

In pedagogy, media competence is generally considered as an integrative quality of a person, which is manifested in the ability to select, critically analyze, evaluate, create and transmit media texts of various forms, genres and forms, as well as the readiness to analyze the complex processes of media activity in society. Therefore, the development of media competence of students of pedagogical higher educational institutions is one of the most important issues facing science and practice. In accordance with the requirements of modern scientific and technical development, the creation of technology for the development of media competence by improving the knowledge of students of pedagogical higher education institutions is of particular importance among pedagogical research.

The concepts of "media education", "media studies" and "media literacy" have now become an integral part of modern education at the school and university level. In the late 1990s, there was the most intense debate in the theoretical and practical framework of pedagogy on the issue of media education. Already in the 1980s, UNESCO declared media education as the priority goal of pedagogy, and the information factor as the leading factor in teaching teenagers and young people at all levels, media education as learning and teaching modern methods of communication and expression. determined.

In the transition to the information society, the non-traditional school model based on education requires the training of personnel based on the social order. In the context of information education, with a sharp increase in the volume of all types of information, each new generation is faced with new conditions that require completely different knowledge. Therefore, a modern educational institution takes on the task of forming a socially active, positive-thinking person, developing the skills and competences of students to use the flow of information correctly, mastering innovative technologies, deepening and expanding knowledge, and learning independently. puts The problem of shifting attention from a knowledgeable approach to a competent approach is especially relevant in terms of modernization of national education. Reforms in education, in the strategy of modernization of the content of higher education, the main result of the activity of the educational institution is not only the system of knowledge, skills and qualifications, but also having a set of basic competencies in civil-legal, linguistic, communication, information and other fields. must be a graduate of

The school should make a lot of efforts to get the teachers in the field of media education from the teachers. A teacher trained in this subject is better able to understand the factors that contribute to the socialization of young people, culture, mass media and their relationships. Media for teaching schoolchildren

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

In Uzbekistan, the problem of forming basic competencies of students is studied by local scientists as one of the main research objects of pedagogy. In particular, R. Kh. Djuraev, A. R. Khodjabaev, N. N. Azizkhodzhaeva, U. I. Inoyatov, N. A. Muslimov, X. F. Rashidov, O'. Q. Tolipov, Sh. S. Sharipov, on the development of competence in using media educational tools among

future teachers. Z.K.Ismailova, Q.T.Olimov, M.B.Urazova, J.A.Hamidov, D.O.Khimmataliev, B.A.Nazarova, B.S.Nuriddinov and others conducted scientific research. By scientists from the CIS countries O.A. Abdulina, L.V. Andropova, Yu.K.Babansky, V.P. Bospalko, S.Ya. Batishev, Ye.M. Borisova, I.V. Grishina, E.F. Zeer, N.V. Kuzmina, S.N. Mironenko, V.A. Slastenin, T.M. Sarokina and others scientific-research works have been carried out on the issues of using pedagogical technologies in the formation and development of professional competence of future vocational education teachers, improving technologies for increasing the effectiveness of vocational-pedagogical training. Creativity in education, development of professional potential of pedagogues, issues of competence, problems of professional-pedagogical maturity, pedagogical special attention is paid to the theory and practical directions of formation and development of skills of using software tools.

The analysis of the scientific-research works of the above-mentioned authors, the organization of the teacher training process in higher education institutions, the teaching of subjects, the state of qualified pedagogical practice shows that the future professional education based on a competent approach the possibilities of improving the technology for the development of professional and pedagogical creativity of teachers are not sufficiently covered, which necessitates the need to research this problem. To determine the methodological and scientific-methodical foundations, principles, and pedagogical conditions of professional-pedagogical creativity of teachers of vocational education based on the requirements of scientific and technical development, to develop technologies for the development of professional-pedagogical creativity based on a competent approach and to practice the need for implementation determines the relevance of research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", No. PQ-2909 of April 20, 2017 "Higher The concept of development of e-commerce in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period of 2016-2018, approved by the Resolution "On measures to further develop the transport system", approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated December 4, 2015 No. 353 This dissertation work serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the complex of activities, as well as other regulatory and legal documents related to this activity. Newspapers, magazines, radio, television, photography, documentary and feature films, news agencies, and the Internet have grown immeasurably in number, and significant changes are taking place in quality. Miracles such as computer, fax, "cellular" phone, parabolic antenna, e-mail have a great influence on the development of mass media. Incomparable opportunities are being created in our country for the training of experts with high intellectual competence, modern knowledge and skills, a new worldview and independent thinking in accordance with the requirements of the times. In this regard, the means of information and communication technologies - television, radio, cinema, video, telephone and other means of communication are showing their effectiveness.

According to experts, media education teaches students to think independently, to further develop creative activities, to receive information, process it, generalize, and draw conclusions. The more perfect the media education is in the educational process, the more it serves the

development of the worldview and intellectual potential of the young generation. So, today it is appropriate to thoroughly study the secrets of media education in theory and apply them in practice. In the conditions of globalization of information and communication, specific requirements are emerging in the educational process. These requirements are directly related to media education.

CONCLUSION. Thus, today, media education is one of the elements of the process of learning professional sciences. It is clear that students need to learn the pedagogical potential of mass media. We will consider the possibility of inclusion in the program of extracurricular activities of the Association of Professional Companies "Modern Media in Education". The direction of modern research is very clearly defined the role of the mass media in the professional training of future teachers. It consists of the development of methodological bases for the organization of media education in an educational institution, the selection and testing of specific tools, mass media, and the appropriate purpose and content of the subject. In addition, to find effective ways to encourage self-education of future teachers in the media. There is great potential for future teachers to develop their media literacy in extracurricular activities. As a community of like-minded people, extracurricular associations help explore and discover the goals, content, and methods of media education. Techniques and means of adequate synthesis of various technologies are the way to increase the efficiency of professional training. Media education technology is organic, value-oriented and in demand in the process of forming the personality of the future teacher. The use of such media educational tools complements each other, and the teachers who use them in their classes are among the modern teachers.

References:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.—T.: "Uzbekistan", 2018.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
3. President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's Address to the Oliy Majlis. (December 28, 2018)
4. R.Kh.Alimov.—Information technology and systems||,T.:2011.-36b.
5. Political text analysis (methodology, theory, practice).—Y.: "Akademiya", 2010.
6. Sharifkhojayev M. Formation of an open civil society in Uzbekistan. — T.: Sharq, 2003.
7. Hazanov I.Y. Tools of media education in the training of future teachers. Media. Information. Communication. 2014.